

RESPONSES TO THE INVITATION FOR PUBLIC COMMENT

Consultation Paper on Health Data Management Policy

31st May 2022

Facilitated by:

The India Digital Health Network,

Lakshmi Mittal and Family South Asia Institute at Harvard University

<https://www.idhnet.org>

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

We are delighted to see the progress with the Ayushman Bharat Health Mission's work and are pleased to provide feedback on the consultation paper for the Health Data Management Policy (HDMP).

This response has been collaboratively drafted by domain experts in health and technology, several of whom have authored earlier responses to the Government of India's National Digital Health Blueprint (NDHB); Personal Data Protection (PDP) Bill; drafts of NITI Aayog's National Health Stack; and recent drafts of NDHM's Health Facilities Registry and Health Professionals Registry (available at: <https://www.idhnet.org/white-papers/>). Responses to consultation papers for [HFR](#)¹, [HPR](#)² and [UHI](#)³ are available here.

The key messages and themes of our comments on the Health Data Management (HDM) are summarized below. We elaborate on these key messages and provide chapter-wise comments and responses in the subsequent sections.

- **Regulatory 'functional' Sandbox:** We recommend the creation and designation of regulatory sandbox environment(s) where current and future digital health interventions can be live tested abiding by HDMP policy. In a sandbox environment, regulators and other ecosystem players could judge the efficacy of various technical, governance and organizational measures to protect privacy and safeguard personal data and detect unintended consequences. This is especially important given how quickly technology evolves and policy must be adapted. Regulators and innovators may also trial promising solutions without stifling innovation.

- **Required enrollment** As we had recommended in our response to the Health Professional and Facility Registries consultation document, please consider requiring enrollment through regulation by appropriate authorities and ministries. Given the large number of unregulated practitioners and facilities across India, required registration can be vitally important in recognizing the credentialed workforce.

We also recommend that health records/documents should be digitally signed and accompany facilities/practitioners enrollment id. This is especially relevant when used in context of computerized provider order entry (CPOE) (e.g. Prescription for scheduled drugs, certain investigative procedures). This will help traceability, auditability, and drive accountability.

¹ IDHN HFR. (2021). Response to the Invitation for Public Comment: Consultation Paper on Healthcare Facilities Registry. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5156511>

² IDHN HPR. (2021). Response to the Invitation for Public Comment: Consultation Paper on Healthcare Professionals Registry. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5156565>

³ Waghmare, A. v, Malhotra, A., Sarkar, A., Luthra, G., Kashyap, S., Rajamani, S., Mohanty, U., & Raj, T. (2021). Response to the Invitation for Public Comment: Consultation Paper on Unified Health Interface (UHI). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5491251>

- **Consent Framework:** While we appreciate the NHA’s effort towards establishment and usage of electronic consent we find several aspects underspecified in this document and recommend elaboration:
 - **No Policy document on HIE-CM:** ABDM has not published any consultation or policy document so far on HIE-CM. This leaves lots of grounds for ambiguity, regarding governance, usage, onboarding/compliance on HIE-CM’s part. Since the HIE-CM is the most significant data fiduciary in the NDHE, touchstone for data consent and data sharing, clarity is needed on governance, accessibility and usage of HIE-CMs.
 - **Expand on Consent Directive, Form and Registration:** We advise ABDM to clearly articulate different types of consents, including usage of electronic consents to help the ecosystem adopt the right means for appropriate context. In the section below, we elaborate means of consenting, different types and applicability and challenges. As an example, a data principal may be able to consent for data donation like organ donation wherein restrictions on data usage are specified if any.
 - **Consent must not absolve data fiduciaries of accountability** - It must not become a tool for compliance for data fiduciaries to make it not liable for any harm it may affect.

- **Expanded Rights of Data Principal:** We recommend the following rights of data principals be considered for inclusion:
 - **Right to be forgotten:** Data principals can request the data fiduciary to erase their personal data. Additionally, they may unlink information about a particular care context at a HIP to their ABHA address. This should also invalidate any relevant consent for data sharing with that HIP.
 - **Right to information:** A data principal should have complete access to the information in their medical record held by a data fiduciary, including most aspects of a medical practitioner’s note - except under specific conditions, agreed upon by the relevant professional oversight bodies. In addition, certain kinds of data, for example operational data, can be exempted. This needs to be clearly defined and agreed upon. Additionally, when a data principal gives consent to an HIU to access their health data, they should be able to see all access attempts using that consent. This would need to be provided by the HIE-CM in real-time as well as in format of logs.⁴ Any data fiduciary may not make it difficult for data principals to access their information through levying fees.
 - **Right to timely access:** Data principal(s) should be able to request and gain access to data held by data fiduciaries in a timely manner. With universal access to health care being basis for the healthcare services, individuals need to be able to give or deny consent for data collection or storage without fear of being denied service delivery or discrimination. Only when people from all strata of life can exercise this right meaningfully, these data protection measures will be of use for

⁴ UIDAI. (n.d.). *Aadhaar Authentication History. Services.* Retrieved June 10, 2022, from <https://resident.uidai.gov.in/aadhaar-auth-history>

everyone. For this to happen the health data management policy could be piloted in small regulatory sandboxes to explore all the pros & cons.⁵

- **Right to restrict processing:** Data principal(s) should be able to restrict certain types of processing of their data so they can limit the secondary uses. As an example, a patient may share their medical history related to HIV for direct medical care but restrict its use for future and alternative uses (like personalized service advertisements). They should be able to choose between a minimal and maximal set of processing options when giving consent to the data fiduciary.
 - **Right to correction/rectification:** Data principal is able to view all personal data collected by the data fiduciary and log a rectification request wherever there is an inaccuracy. Data fiduciary cannot make this substantially complex or burdensome to do.
 - **Right to be notified:** Data principals should be notified in case there is any change in privacy policy or data management policy of any data fiduciary in NDHE. Since the HIE-CM's consent artefact can be used to fetch data many times, HIE-CM should also notify the patient (SMS or alternate means) anytime data is accessed by means of a consent.
- **Registries of Data Fiduciaries** We want to re-emphasize inclusion of all health data fiduciaries onto HFR or publicly available registries, which may be interlinked. Currently, HFR is largely focused on facilities with some physical presence. This focus misses the industry trend toward a growing proportion of healthcare being delivered virtually, in home-based settings, and through a mix of physical and digital services. While the policy document references HFR and HPR and their relevance as data fiduciaries, it does not outline how HIE-CM entities like HIU, HIP, HRP, Health Lockers, PHRs etc are to be governed. Similarly proposed entities in UHI context like EUAs, HSPAs are also data fiduciaries and we would recommend that future iteration of the policy specify how these will be registered, managed, identified or discovered.
 - **Privacy Assurance Framework** We are incredibly pleased to see NHA's intent and efforts towards privacy, however we think there is a lot of overlap amongst different initiatives amongst government bodies and thereby confusion regarding dealing with privacy and data protection in the ecosystem. We recommend that NHA brings assimilation from other parallel initiatives in India to form a comprehensive Privacy Assurance Framework for entities in the NDHE. Two such important frameworks are BIS 17428⁶ and MeitY's draft National Data Governance Policy.⁷ Also, wherever possible data masking/redaction could be used to improve privacy
 - **Anonymized/research data:** Main objective of collecting data is to improve healthcare delivery, gain knowledge through research, statistical analysis, and policy formulation.

⁵ UIDAI. (n.d.). Aadhaar Authentication History. Services. Retrieved June 10, 2022, from <https://resident.uidai.gov.in/aadhaar-auth-history>

⁶ GoI. (2020). 2 THE GAZETTE OF INDIA: BIS 17428. 1–22. <http://www.standardsbis.in>

⁷ MeITY. (2022). National Data Governance Framework Policy (Draft). 1–9.

Data anonymized and prepared for achieving these objectives needs to use more robust methods than standard de-identification methods. These offer limited guarantees for preserving the privacy of individuals in research databases; the risk of re-identification increases the more data is processed. In contrast, differential privacy algorithms offer ways to limit privacy loss and bound it within certain limits. We recommend NHA in consultation with MeitY consider such methods.⁸ Data should also follow the FAIR principles of being findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. Consent for research use should also be as broad as possible; though consent may be revoked by the data principal. The challenge is to avoid misuse of such a broad consent for commercial exploitation and/or discrimination of certain populations. Hence, we recommend that policy be drafted to regulate commercial uses of anonymized data. Also, for data to be findable by larger audiences, metadata need to be published, be accessible digitally, and must be interoperable. Some useful resources are:

- The OpenDP Platform: <https://privacytools.seas.harvard.edu/opensdp>
- Dataverse: <https://dataverse.org/>

- **References to policies and documentation:** The consultation paper refers to many concepts, constructs while articulating the policies and guidelines. For the uninitiated and not well versed with the ABDM initiatives, it becomes difficult to laboriously search/query reference documents on the internet and ABDM website, and then read through the sections within - thus taking a lot of time. It would be great if consultation papers would also provide reference/links to relevant documents and pointing to sections within.

We are very grateful for the time, attention and counsel provided by all contributing authors. And finally, we thank the NDHM and NHA for this opportunity to respond to the consultation paper on Health Facility Registry.

Sincerely,
On behalf of the contributing authors,

Dr. Tony D S Raj, MBBS, MD
Dean, St. John's Research
Institute
Head, Division of Medical
Informatics, St. John's
Research Institute

Satchit Balsari, MD, MPH
Assistant Professor, Emergency
Medicine, Harvard Medical
School;
Director, India Digital Health
Network, Lakshmi Mittal South
Asia Institute at Harvard

**Angshuman Sarkar,
B.E**
Principal Consultant,
Global Health Practice
Lead, Thoughtworks
Technologies

⁸ CrisisReady. (2021). OpenDP: open-source software tools for privacy-protective statistical analysis of sensitive personal data. <https://www.crisisready.io/2020/opensdp-open-source-software-tools-for-privacy-protective-statistical-analysis-of-sensitive-personal-data/>

The India Digital Health Network,
Lakshmi Mittal and Family South Asia Institute at Harvard University

CONTRIBUTORS

Name	Organization
Dr. Abijeet V Waghmare	St. John's Research Institute
Dr. Akhil Malhotra	Thoughtworks India
Mr. Angshuman Sarkar	Thoughtworks India
Dr. Satchit Balsari	Harvard Medical School
Dr. Sehj Kashyap	Clinikk
Dr. Tony Raj	Professor and Dean, St. John's Research Institute

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Name	Organization
Rev. Dr. J. Charles Davis.	Associate Director, College and Research, St. John's Medical College & St. John's Research Institute
Dr. Olinda Tims	Division of Health and Humanities St. John's Research Institute
Dr. Manjulika Vaz	Division of Health and Humanities St. John's Research Institute

Glossary of Terms

Term	Definition
ABDM/NDHM	Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission/National Digital Health Mission
ABHA	Ayushman Bharat Health Account
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning
API	Application Programming Interface
BIS	Bureau of Indian Standards
CPOE	Computerized Provider Order Entry
DPA	Data Protection Authority
DPEA	Data Empowerment And Protection Architecture
eKYC	electronic Know Your Customer
EUA	End User Application
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HCX	Health Claim Exchange
HDM	Health Data Management
HFR	Health Facilities Registry
HIE-CM	Healthcare Information Exchange - Consent Manager
HIP	Health Information Provider
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
HIU	Health Information User
HPR	Health Professionals Registry
HRP	Health Repository Provider
HSPA	Health Service Provider Applications
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol

IEC	Information, Education, Communication
IVR	Interactive Voice Response
NDHB	National Digital Health Blueprint
NDHE	National Digital Health Eco-system
NHA	National Health Authority
NHS	National Health Service
OPD	Outpatient Department
PAN	Permanent Account Number
PDP	Personal Data Protection
PHR	Personal Health Record
RBI	Reserve Bank of India
SMS	Short Messaging Services
UHI	Unified Health Interface
USSD	Unstructured Supplementary Service Data

Elaboration of summary points

Regulatory ‘Functional’ Sandbox

We commend NHA for the sandbox process⁹, and appreciate the role it brings in terms of testing with dummy data, assert interoperability with representative ecosystems and act as a clearing-house mechanism. Extending beyond the existing process, we recommend that NHA create a regulatory sandbox process to test various aspects of the proposed health data management policy.

A regulatory sandbox allows regulators, innovators and service providers and the patients to conduct field tests of proposed policies and technologies and collect evidence on the benefits and risks of innovations while carefully monitoring and containing risks. A regulatory sandbox can be set up by relaxing existing regulations for a defined time period within a particular jurisdiction. An innovator could apply for exemption to a specific regulation for the purpose of testing but approval would not mean a blanket exemption and remainder regulations and law would still apply. As an example, a state agency could test an AI algorithm to automate community-based patient health monitoring before rolling it out en masse.

India has precedence of establishing such Regulatory Sandbox process¹⁰ in FinTech regulated by RBI. The proposed PDP Bill 2019 in clause 40 also mentions the context of regulatory sandbox.

We believe several use cases proposed in the HDM policy should be tested through a regulatory sandbox process :

1. Consent Framework: Different means of securing consent could be tested for their effectiveness and impacts on different sets of population. The use of AI/ML during consent could be tested to help vulnerable populations give informed consent.
2. Technology Innovation: A.I. consultation based on personal medical history. e.g University Hospitals Birmingham NHS Foundation Trust employs “Ask E&E”, an AI powered consultation service
3. AI/ML for Syndromic surveillance, fraud detection, security and data breach etc
4. Data anonymization and data hubs: Different approaches to anonymizing personal health data and making it available to researchers could be tested and evaluated for their privacy and security implications.

⁹ Bhatia A, Matthan R, Khanna T, Balsari S. Regulatory Sandboxes: A Cure for mHealth Pilotitis? *J Med Internet Res.* 2020 Sep 15;22(9):e21276. doi: 10.2196/21276. PMID: 32763889; PMCID: PMC7525408. Accessed at <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32763889/>

¹⁰ RBI. (n.d.). *Enabling Framework for Regulatory Sandboxes. Framework.* Retrieved June 10, 2022, from <https://rbi.org.in/Scripts/PublicationReportDetails.aspx?UrlPage=&ID=1187>

Consent Framework and HIE-CM

We believe that Electronic Consent and enabled services have huge potential, bring benefits and unforeseen implications and behaviors in the healthcare ecosystem and on part of the data principal. Electronic consent therefore must be carefully expanded and elaborated in definitions of directive it encodes, form and format including rules and conditions it embeds, and means of securing/registering, many of which this policy document elucidates. .

There are multiple types of consent and authorization based on contextual usage. For example, HIE-CM itself has multiple types of authorization and consenting workflows and means.

- Access to health records is granted to a requester through a “*Consent Artifact*”, a directive that lays out control for data sharing
- For enabling subscribers (a doctor keeping up to date on patients, a Health Locker for archiving records) - patient must also “consent” to send notifications to subscribers (HIUs and HLs),
- A patient may also “consent” for eKYC validation etc.

On the provider side, a patient may consent digitally/verbally for data collection and processing. These consents are not the same as “Electronic Consent” for HIE-CM but should extend the same rights to the patient.

Means of consenting:

Electronic consent features through HIE-CM only caters to apps which require accessibility to a smart phone and internet. This brings limitations to a significant part of our population for granting / revoking consents for data access. For inclusion and equity, there must be alternate means of securing consent like SMS, IVR or Network initiated USSD. For those, who cannot use such electronic routes, meaningful assisted means of consenting must be devised, and perhaps tested and validated in a regulatory sandbox as discussed above

Our reflection on other consenting means is described here::

Delegated consent: As indicated in this policy document, there also needs to be “nominated” persons in case of minors, seriously ill, incapacitated etc, to make consents on behalf of the data principal. There must be due process for such delegation to nominees depending on relation/association - parents, relations, carer etc.

Deemed consent: For scenarios like emergency cases, where the data principal is incapacitated to provide consent and no nominee or relations are available / present, we think it is appropriate to provision an automatic “deemed” consent. However, in such cases, the consent generated must

be limited to purpose, one-time-usage, time-duration and potentially subjected to the profile of the requester. Furthermore, there needs to be tracking and observation of such requesters so that deemed consent mechanisms are not abused.

Another aspect to note, as we commented in our response to the [UHI consultation paper](#)¹¹, there is also the aspect of "awareness/meaning of consent" and whether anyone 18+ may be trusted to give "consent" under context; e.g. mentally ill, uneducated, lack of awareness, coercion etc. We must not assume that even the educated and able have the knowledge, awareness of her rights and exercise options, and is aware of implications of consent and consequences.

While the Government must keep doing a lot on IEC (information, education, communication), we should also leverage community knowledge and technology to help data principals make informed consent decisions. Innovations on the PHR application side can assist/sensitize the data principal towards their rights. Organizations, initiatives and technology-enabled guidance will be needed to sensitize data principals about data sharing risks and benefits.

With increasing interoperability and collaboration in healthcare services, and usage of technology like big data, AI/ML etc, consent is increasingly becoming porous and may even be amorphous. We cannot predict how interconnected information and correlations to datasets fetched through disparate consents would impact us and our privacy. Add to that, the issue of consent fatigue, and cases where users would probably just accept a long drawn, indecipherable ambiguous privacy disclaimer/notice because without the acceptance of such consent, a particular benefit or service can not be leveraged. While consent is a powerful tool towards an individual's choice of exercising options towards personal data, fiduciaries must still be accountable irrespective of consent, notice, purpose limitations. Consent must not become a tool for compliance for data fiduciaries to make it not liable for any harm it may affect.

Our recommendations on Consent, Privacy and Usability of data are best represented in our work here:

Saksena N, Matthan R, Bhan A, Balsari S. Rebooting consent in the digital age: a governance framework for health data exchange. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2021 Jul;6(Suppl 5):e005057. doi: 10.1136/bmjgh-2021-005057. PMID: 34301754; PMCID: PMC8728384. Accessed at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34301754/>

and

Balsari et al. The Use of Human Mobility Data in Public Health Emergencies
https://2xvqgv2bq8at1ugrhyfyqan1-wpengine.netdna-ssl.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/CR_The-Use-of-Human-Mobility-Data-in-Pub-Health-Emergencies.pdf

¹¹ *Waghmare, A. v, Malhotra, A., Sarkar, A., Luthra, G., Kashyap, S., Rajamani, S., Mohanty, U., & Raj, T. (2021). Response to the Invitation for Public Comment: Consultation Paper on Unified Health Interface (UHI). https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5491251*

HIE-CM is the cornerstone for electronic consent enabling consented means of data sharing and access and key to patient rights. Towards this, we request NHA to elaborate on

- Representation of HIE-CM: Currently only the NHA will host a HIE-CM in the ecosystem. Would other public or private entities be allowed to operate other HIE-CMs in the network?
- Access to HIE-CM: Access to ABDM network is typically done through the ABDM gateway, However, ABDM Sandbox documentation indicate that HIE-CM APIs are open for consumption by PHR apps - if so, this document does not elaborate on patients' authorization process from a PHR app to manage her consents. Or for that matter, the registration and compliance of such PHR apps.

Security Practices and Procedures

We would also like to recommend certain improvements towards “consent” and enabled practices from a security and best practices lens.

1. Encrypt API Payloads: All API payloads, irrespective of routing systems and networks involved, must be encrypted. This is significant as data in ABDM networks move through public networks. While the federated health records architecture of ABDM HIE-CM ensures that data is stored at origin and all health records data is encrypted when eventually exchanged, there exists many workflows where APIs carry significant meta information which when tapped can potentially reveal information of data principal. ABDM APIs follow a asynchronous call-back pattern contrary to the typical HTTP request-response APIs, and we must not assume that any intermediary (e.g. ABDM Gateway, HRP Bridges/Gateways) is not tapping information. For example, during “self-discovery” of a patient's health records, basic patient demographic information along with identifiers and contact details are sent through ABDM gateway and through HRP, before the intended HIP receives the information. During this process, HRPs can unpack the information and use it for other unwanted purposes (e.g. send marketing messages). Another example is the notification from HIP carrying a phone number and message - which again, if tapped, can cause harm to the data principal (e.g. phishing).
2. Use Digital Certificates: We recommend usage of Digital Certificate for HIP/HIU identification. ABDM network allows a Health Repository Provider (HRP) to represent several HIPs and HIUs, and ABDM Gateway only authenticates HRPs in such cases. This may leave potential gaps where a HRP can employ unfair means of faking a request coming from a legitimate HIP. Usage of digital certificates and encryption can eliminate such risks and enable identification of HIP/HIUs.
3. Use eSigning: We also recommend that NHA over time mandate usage of Digital Signing for issued health documents. For certain operations/services like CPOE (e.g. dispensation of drugs, radiological tests), specific clinical documents, usage of eSigning should be advised. Non-repudiation will be guaranteed by digital signatures, driving trust, and improving patient safety.
4. In an API driven digital ecosystem, protocols while enabling workflows, should safeguard against phishing / baiting/ Pretexting social-engineering attacks.

Privacy Assurance Framework

With a flourishing data economy and increasing collaboration and system integration, India is challenged with safeguarding patient privacy and safety. Without specific acts like HIPAA or GDPR, we rely on consumer protection laws, telecommunications statutes, human rights provisions, and other measures to address data breaches and privacy violations. With the understanding that the HDM Policy draws a lot of inspiration from the proposed PDP Bill 2019, we advise that NHA brings assimilation from other parallel initiatives in India to form a comprehensive Privacy Assurance Framework for entities in the NDHE. Two such important frameworks are

- June 2021, Bureau of India Standards (BIS) introduced IS 17428¹² for data privacy assurance. Composed in 2 parts, part 1 of IS 17428 deals with the management and engineering parameters that are expected for organizations to comply with. Part 1 provides for establishing and cultivating a competent Data Privacy Management System.
- May 2022, MeitY came out with a draft National Data Governance Policy¹³ to be applicable to Government department and entities with objectives to have standardized data management and security standards and to accelerate creation of common standard based public digital platforms while ensuring privacy, safety, and trust.

With multiple such standards and drafts, there is confusion and ambiguity as to what applies and what to adopt. Also, with the Data protection bill under review and with a Data Protection Authority (DPA) envisaged to be constituted under the legislation to have the power to issue code, guidelines, and best practices for protecting the privacy of data principals, NHA needs to have a mechanism to continuously review and align with applicable laws/regulations and policies which are expected to evolve as technology and usage rapidly changes.

¹² *GoI. (2020). 2 THE GAZETTE OF INDIA: BIS 17428. 1–22.* <http://www.standardsbis.in>

¹³ *MeITy. (2022). National Data Governance Framework Policy (Draft). 1–9*
<https://www.meity.gov.in/content/draft-national-data-governance-framework-policy>

Other Comments

Comments on Chapter I: Preliminary

- **Section 1 Purpose:** mentions *“For creating an integrated, uniform and interoperable ecosystem in a patient or individual centric manner, all the government healthcare facilities and programs, in a gradual/phased manner, should start assigning the same number for providing any benefit to individual. This number, created with KYC using Aadhaar or any other digital system, will be known as Ayushman Bharat Health Account (ABHA (number))”*

We want to stress that such registration and assignment must strictly be optional unto patients/beneficiaries. In no context should such an “number” or “identifier” be considered necessary towards any care services for the patient. Facilities’ systems must not rely on the ABHA number as an identifier, and should be able to service an individual through hospital record number/patient/customer id. For the purpose of leveraging the NDHE services/domains, only ABHA/PHR address should be optionally linked, and not necessarily the ABHA number itself, as a given ABHA number may be linked to many PHR addresses, and a user may have multiple ABHA numbers¹⁴.

- **Section 2 Applicability:** We recommend that ABDM describes and maintains a comprehensive list of entities that this policy would be applicable to. For example - “At home-care”, “health tech product” entities should be included. In Section 2 j) please also include “social media”, “chats/Instant messaging.”
- We request NHA to clarify whether this policy applies to entities who do not interface with data principals but operate in private arrangement with the data fiduciary. Such entities should be deemed as “data processors” and specifically listed. Note, the same seems to be suggested in other sections of the policy document (e.g. Section 27.2, Transparency and Accountability measures)).
- Please clarify whether “Applicability” also covers cases where health/personal data is collected on paper or printed out and further duplicated and transmitted.
- **Section 4 Definitions:** For clause 4h defining data fiduciary, we recommend to include entities like HIU, HIP, HRP, HIE-CM, PHR apps, Health Lockers, and also EUAs and HSPAs etc in a comprehensive list.
- **Section 4.o,** we would request that “harm” definitions should have comprehensive list/examples. For example, we opine that the following are also suitable
 - Any adverse effect due to withholding, incorrectness or non-availability of information.
 - Any psychosocial issues due to undue access leading to revealing of sensitive data
- **Section 4.p,** in the definition of “Health Facility” please include nursing homes, maternity homes, day-care facilities, rehabilitation centres, geriatric centres, dispensaries, sanatoriums, home healthcare companies, telemedicine and cloud providers.

¹⁴ NHA. (2022, February 26). ABHA FAQs. <https://abha.abdm.gov.in/FAQ>

- **Section 4.r**, in the definition of “Health Information Provider”, please include entities like nursing homes, maternity homes, day-care facilities
- **Section 4.w**, please clarify that a “nominee” authorization is pertaining to specific purposes. For example, a nominated person may grant emergency consent approval in “break the glass” scenarios, can the same nomination be used for “opting out” or “delinking a specific record”.
- **Section 4.bb**, Please mention whether “Personal Health Record Applications” are also expected to manage consents regarding data requests, subscriptions and authorization for KYC
- **Section 4.cc**, regarding “processing”, please clarify on “disclosure with transmission”, whether confidentiality be affected.

Comments on Chapter II: Entities under the NDHE, Applicable Law and Governance Structure

1. **Section 6 Governance Structure** does not clarify which entity will act as Data Protection Authority (DPA). To ensure that the DPA carries its duties without bias, we recommend that the DPA must be an autonomous body and must not be a data fiduciary.

Comments on Chapter III: Consent Framework

1. **Section 7 mentions:** “Data fiduciaries can collect personal data, which shall be limited to such data that is necessary for the purposes specified under Clause 9.3 of this Policy.” We recommend the section be reframed as “Data fiduciaries can collect personal data with due consent from a data principal, which shall be limited to such data that is necessary for the purposes specified under Clause 9.3 of this Policy.”
2. **Section 8.b** refers to electronic consent. It is not clear how other forms of consent viz. hand-written informed consent; implied consents shall be handled. Please also elaborate what constitutes an “electronic consent.” Electronic consents could differ in directive, form and registration and there needs to be specification of what counts as valid and align it with the MeitY’s DEPA architecture.
3. **Section 9.2**, We recommend that a log or ledger of all consents provided must be preserved by fiduciaries for a reasonably sufficient period of time for audit trails
4. **Section 9.3** does not clearly mention the list and the definitions of purposes as mentioned in section 7. Looking at the “Purpose of Use” as mentioned in documentation for ABDM¹⁵, it is not clear who defines the purposes and contexts, and whether specific purposes apply to specific types of requesters, and how future propositions for “purpose of use” would be handled?
5. **Section 10.2 (g)** mentions “...or where the period of retention is not known, then the criteria for determining such period”
We opine that the period of data retention must always be mentioned otherwise it leaves a window for the data fiduciaries to indefinitely retain the data by carefully wording the privacy notice.
6. With reference to **Section 10.2 (i)**, we recommend HIE-CM should provide a means for PHR app users or any EUAs (end user applications) to discover the data fiduciary’s contact information.
7. With reference to **Section 11.1**, We recommend that NHA
 - Expand the means of capture of consent: HIE-CM currently supports only consenting through an app. To enable for the population and scenarios, where a mobile app or internet access is not available to the data principal, we suggest evaluation of SMS, IVR or Network initiated USSD as alternate means.

¹⁵ NHA. (n.d.). NDHM Sandbox API. Documentation. Retrieved June 10, 2022, from <https://sandbox.abdm.gov.in/docs/apis>

- We also recommend that for the cases where a data principal requires assistance or is limited, alternate means of consent like “delegated consent”, “deemed consent” is provided. Please refer to the “Consent Framework and HIE-CM” section for more details. .
8. **Section 11.2.b**, Please clarify whether by “consent logs/consent transactions” include audit logs for “data access” for a given consent. A data principal must be to see which party accessed her data at what time based on what consent and status of such enabled transactions.
 9. **Section 11.4**, mentions “ *.... electronic consent is the digital equivalent of a physical letter of permission given by the data principal which, when presented, **allows the HIE-CM or the data fiduciary to collect the personal data, or further process the personal data ...** ”. Please clarify whether HIE-CM can access health records using consent. Electronic consent for health data access is given to a HIU (a data fiduciary) alone and to none else. HIE-CMs should be allowed only to store linkage of patient records and have minimal PII data (name, gender, contact, location etc).*
 10. **Section 13.3**, Please elaborate within NDHE, how HIE-CM would recognize the nominee/family member to enable the consent.
 11. **Section 13.5**, A list of exceptional situations must be provided, or it must be clearly defined who decides if the situation is exceptional and on what criteria.
 12. **Section 13.5(b)**, This section needs elaboration. A list of criteria must be specified, else, there is a potential for this section to be misused. Data principals (HIV patients, Mental Health patients, TB patients, Leprosy patients. STDs etc.) could be stigmatized.
 13. **Section 14.1(a)(iii)**, mentions “ *The data principal shall also have the right to access in one place the identities of all the data fiduciaries with whom her/his personal data has been shared by any data fiduciary together with the categories of personal data that has been shared.*”
Does it include the data subsequently shared downstream by a data fiduciary - e.g. to data processors?
 14. **Section 14.2(a)**, This clause excludes the vast majority of the Indian population that does not have the literacy or the means to escalate the issue meaningfully. We highly recommend that there be simpler and meaningful alternatives like IVR, verbal chatbots for data principals to exercise their rights. .
 15. **Section 14.2(d)**, states “ *In the event that any request is rejected, the data fiduciary will provide the data principal reasons in writing for such refusal. If the data principal is not satisfied with such reasons, it may require that the data fiduciary take reasonable steps to indicate, alongside the relevant personal data, that the same is disputed by the data principal.*”
 - a. The broad categories for rejection or refusal should be defined and regulated by the NHA and not left up to data fiduciaries. Otherwise, data fiduciaries may exploit their ability to reject data principals’ request for data.

This would be similar to information blocking exemptions specified in the Cures Act in the US¹⁶.

- b. Looking at the API standards for HIE-CM and PHR app, we understand HIE-CM does not yet have any capability yet to indicate the dispute between data fiduciary and the data principal. This document should elaborate if this provision shall be added in HIE-CM.

Comments on Chapter IV: ABHA & Other ID Policy

1. **Section 16.2**, Please clarify if private medical institutions will also be allowed to issue ABHA (Numbers) to patients visiting their facilities.
2. **Section 17.2**, Ability to delink ABHA address is also desired, both through HIE-CM and from HIP (with due authorization from data principal).
3. **Section 18.2**, As understood HIE-CM is not open yet. All HIE-CMs must agree to the NDHE standards and protocols. If this is beyond the scope of the document - NHA should consider bringing out a similar consultation paper on HIE-CM - compliance and regulatory requirements, conformance/governance etc.
4. **Section 19.2**, As we understand, currently ABHA number can only be obtained with Aadhaar, Driving License, PAN etc. Please elaborate what alternate methods are proposed e.g. Voter Id, Passport, Ration card, Birth Certificate etc.
5. **Section 20.5**, We recommend that in certain functions and documents, NHA articulate “should-have” usage of Digital Signatures. We understand that NHA does not create any restrictions towards service delivery - however, for certain operations/services like CPOE, specific clinical documents, usage of eSigning should be advised. Non-repudiation will be guaranteed by digital signatures, driving trust and improving patient safety. For records originating from institutional setup (facilities), they should carry the Facility ID and signatures.
6. **Section 21.1**, Referring to our response of section 20.5, healthcare professionals should require digital verification for data access and collection/generation, (e.g view patient records, advise tests/order meds)
 - a. for such CPOE to be acted upon (e.g. scheduled drugs can only be given on doctor’s prescription)
 - b. for adjudication of medico-legal cases, e.g. where information could be released to unverified requesters or health information generated was forged by unverified users.

If done from institutional setups (like hospitals/facilities), such information may be signed by the authorised representatives of the facility; if done from private capacity, then Professional ID or digital signature should be included, with friction less user experience.

7. **Section 22.2**, While participation in NDHE could be optional, but to participate in NDHE (either as individuals leveraging UHI or HIE-CM for access), NHA should mandate that

¹⁶ *HealthIT.gov. (n.d.). Information Blocking Exceptions. 1–5.*
<https://www.healthit.gov/cures/sites/default/files/cures/2020-03/InformationBlockingExceptions.pdf>

professionals require Professional ID.

8. **Section 24.1**, Like we commented in the response to HFR consultation document, *"The scope of the HFR needs to be expanded. Currently, it is largely focused on facilities with some physical presence. This focus misses the industry trend toward a growing proportion of healthcare being delivered virtually, in home-based settings, and through a mix of physical and digital services. Telemedicine, online pharmacies, home-care agencies must be included in the HFR registry"*

In addition, health tech organizations, like PHR apps, personalized care apps, Health Lockers or HSPA/ EUAs in UHI, must also be included as they can have access to personal health data. We request NHA to:

- expand the scope of the HFR beyond facilities with physical presence
- create separate registry for such entities

Comments on Chapter V: Obligations of Data Fiduciaries in relation to Processing of Personal Data

1. **Section 26.1 Accountability**, While we agree with the consent framework in principle, we recognize that it is unclear how it will play out in the real world. It is therefore imperative that aspects of the framework are rolled out in controlled settings in limited spatial scope, with community awareness and consent.
"Consent" must not be a "tool" for safeguarding against liability for any intended or unintended harm caused directly or indirectly. For this we must have strong accountability measures, where data fiduciaries must still be accountable irrespective of consent, notice, purpose limitations, as we have argued in the referenced paper here, "Rebooting Consent."
2. **Section 26.2 f Transparency** mentions according rating or data trust score for data fiduciaries. Please elaborate on the approach for establishing a fair scoring mechanism, availability of such information to the data principal and the entity/organization and the process for arriving at such a score.
3. **Section 26.2 Transparency** also mentions that data fiduciaries should notify data principals on important operations in the processing of any personal data. The term "important operations" is vague; please consider being more specific or providing illustrative examples. Please also clarify what would be the means (and timeframe) of notifications to data principals - especially without primary digital devices.
4. **Section 26.6 Storage Limitation** indicates that data fiduciaries are to remove data post processing and as per the retention policy of the consent. Please note, that while such erasure may be possible when data is fetched from other facilities, it may not be always possible at the source - due to regulations and system requirements e.g. Diagnostic Report for COVID19, or removal of billing information affecting accounting. However, It is possible to anonymize PII information. NHA should provide guidance as to what residual information and type is allowed in such cases.
5. **Section 26.8 Data Quality**, We suggest that the data fiduciary or Data processor should be held responsible for any errors that occur in the data during processing. There should

be a mechanism to penalize fiduciaries or processors if it was evident that the data were deliberately changed during processing, leading to false conclusions.

Data quality reflects on the “Integrity” part of Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability (CIA) triad and involves maintenance consistency, accuracy and trustworthiness of data over its entire lifecycle. To enable downstream collaborators in processing information, we recommend that “Provenance statements” be associated with digital health records while sharing information, describing entities and processes involved in producing or influencing the information. Such provenance statements have clinical significance in terms of confidence in authenticity, reliability, and trustworthiness, integrity, and stage in lifecycle, all of which may impact security, privacy, and trust policies.

6. **Section 27.2**, While laying out the compliance requirements across all data fiduciaries in the NDHE is beyond the scope of the document, we would urge NHA to provide indicative data governance and compliance guidelines. We would urge NHA to devise incentives and means where upholding “standards for data privacy” is given like a Quality badge to data fiduciaries, (allocated by independent bodies every year, e.g Quality Control of India or HIPAA, HONcode), and such can be taken into consideration by data principals while consenting or providing information.
7. **Section 27.3 Data Protection Impact Assessment**, We recommend that data fiduciaries be required to publish such assessments annually, and not only at the time of initial certification. Such Information on relevant data fiduciary registries should be taken into consideration for arriving at any “Quality Score”
8. **Section 27.5 Audit**, we appreciate the clause 27.5.c, for this ensures immutability of recorded information - especially in the context of clinical information. We recommend that any mutation of data, must be notified to the data principal.

Comments on Chapter VI: Sharing of Personal Data and Obligations of Entities with whom Personal Data is Shared

1. **Section 29**, We recommend that anonymized data sets be shared widely - if not publicly - with an authorized community of users, including academic institutions, innovators, and other key stakeholders in the health care delivery ecosystem.
2. **Section 29.1**, Regarding de-identified aggregate data formation, since de-identification may not be sufficient with the ability of AI/ML to draw correlations and inferences, while anonymization may result in loss of scientifically important data, we request NHA come up with a guidance on anonymisation. Please also refer to our comments on “Differential Privacy” regarding anonymized/research data. The tension between utility and privacy may be best balanced by a combination of technical and legal tools, as we have outlined in our paper “Rebooting Consent.”
3. **Section 30.2**, We recommend that NHA brings in improvements to assist the data principal in providing granular specificity for types of information a HIU/HIP can access/share. Right now HIE-CM’s “Consent Artefact” has provision to mention only broad level record types (e.g. OPD record, prescription, diagnostic report etc” but does not ability to indicate any

filter or granular rule - for example - share only “Pathology report” or “Microbiology Report”, do not share “OPD record of mental health screening encounter” or “Mental health” history etc

4. **Section 30.4**, Please clarify whether 30.4 a, implies maintaining a complete audit trail of access of data and use of data, to all humans and computers.
5. **Section 30.4**, We would also request that HIUs respect consent for individual requesters. HIE-CM’s consent artefact has provision for specifying requesters (Doctor, healthcare professionals) besides the entity or organization (e.g a facility or a payor), and if “consent” is so given, then only the granted “requester” individuals be allowed access.

Comments on Chapter VII: Grievance Redressal and Compliance

1. **Section 32**, ABDM has many data repositories (e.g. core registries) and domain services (e.g. HIE-CM, upcoming UHI and HCX) and ecosystem data fiduciaries participating in the NDHE for different services. We urge NHA to clearly elaborate on the levels and means of escalation across all domain services.
2. **Section 32**, We also recommend that every EUAs (end user applications) be mandated to clearly communicate means and levels of escalation for the benefits of data principals.

Other Comments

1. Since healthcare applications or Healthtech products can be created by any entity, Indian or foreign, there would be cases where foreign entities will act as data fiduciaries. How will these policies apply to foreign entities? To what extent?
2. We recommend keeping an audit log of all the consent provided by the data principal.
3. It is not clear how the privacy of data of the potentially vulnerable/sensitive groups, for example, HIV patients, indigenous tribes etc. will be reviewed.
4. We recommend adding another clause to section 14.1(a): “The data fiduciary will provide information on where the data principal’s data is stored in a repository.”

APPENDIX 1

White Papers: Responses to previous public consultations by the government

- IDHN. (2020, February). Responses to the Government of India's Joint Parliamentary Committee's Consultation on the Personal Data Protection Bill. Response. <https://bif5m4023k53ib5vt30v2wu8-wpengine.netdna-ssl.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/IDHN-Comments-on-PDP-Bill.pdf>
- IDHN. (2018, February 1). Responses To The White Paper Of The Committee Of Experts On Data Protection Framework For India: A Lens On Health Data. Response. <https://cdn1.sph.harvard.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/2464/2019/08/Harvard-Response-WP-Health-Data-Protection.pdf>
- Gupta, A., Waghmare, A., Gropper, A., Sarkar, A., Sethuraman, A. v, Varma, D., Pandey, D., Singh, H., Antony, J., Halamka, J., Arora, N., Saksena, N., Matthan, R., Balsari, S., Vaidhyam, S., Nadhamuni, S., Sarbadhikari, S., Khanna, T., Raj, T., & Divan, V. (2019). Response To The Invitation For Public Comment National Digital Health Blueprint. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5259999>
- IDHN HFR. (2021). Response to the Invitation for Public Comment: Consultation Paper on Healthcare Facilities Registry. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5156511>
- IDHN HPR. (2021). Response to the Invitation for Public Comment: Consultation Paper on Healthcare Professionals Registry. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5156565>
- Waghmare, A. v, Malhotra, A., Sarkar, A., Luthra, G., Kashyap, S., Rajamani, S., Mohanty, U., & Raj, T. (2021). Response to the Invitation for Public Comment: Consultation Paper on Unified Health Interface (UHI). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5491251>

Scientific Articles

- Saksena N, Matthan R, Bhan A, et al Rebooting consent in the digital age: a governance framework for health data exchange *BMJ Global Health* 2021;6:e005057. Accessed at https://gh.bmj.com/content/6/Suppl_5/e005057
- Bhatia A, Matthan R, Khanna T, Balsari S. Regulatory Sandboxes: A Cure for mHealth Pilotitis? *J Med Internet Res*. 2020 Sep 15;22(9):e21276. doi: 10.2196/21276. PMID: 32763889; PMCID: PMC7525408. Accessed at <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32763889/>